

Action Plan of Research Assessment at the University of Freiburg

29th of April 2026

1. Research Assessment at the University of Freiburg: Institutional Context

The University of Freiburg (UFR) is one of the most renowned comprehensive universities in Germany and covers a broad interdisciplinary spectrum of high-quality research, teaching and transfer activities. To us, quality in academia means constantly developing and incessantly questioning knowledge. Our basic and applied research and the development of problem-solving expertise are indispensable in this endeavor and highly depend on the excellence of our researchers and their commitment, on innovative research outputs and the efficiency of our research-performing entities.

Due to the broad variety of disciplines and research cultures at our university, we are aware about the well-established practices, tools and mechanisms of research assessment within different scientific contexts. However, as an institution, we strive to safeguard quality by developing adequate, fair and transparent conditions for research assessment on the long run.¹ We are convinced that it takes a shift towards practices including qualitative methods to adequately assess researchers, research outputs and research-performing entities.

To achieve this, the UFR became a member of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) in May 2025. The University signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA)² in consensus with the Academic Senate, which is the central body of academic self-government and represents researchers from various disciplines and all career stages. We thereby have committed to critically reviewing and reflecting on our existing practices and mechanisms of Research Assessment in relation to the principles outlined in ARRA. This CoARA-Action Plan has been adopted and approved by the two central bodies of our institution, the Rectorate and the Senate, in April 2026.

¹ <https://uni-freiburg.de/en/university/portrait/mission-statement/>.

² See <https://www.coara.org/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/> and <https://zenodo.org/records/13480728>.

As the impact of an institutional action plan highly depends on its concrete benefit to the people concerned, their needs were taken into account in particular when it was drawn up as part of a participatory process within our institution. In developing the ARRA principles, we were also considering the specific features and the governance structure of our institution. Our eleven faculties play a key role in recruiting academic staff and thus in regularly assessing researchers and their research outputs. When designing our Action Plan for Reforming Research Assessment on an institutional level and elaborating on our fields of action, we strive to meet the specificities that each faculty and its disciplines entail.

On an institutional level, we are building upon a leadership structure that is highly in favour of evolving crosscutting topics like Research Assessment: The institutional project of Reforming Research Assessment in line with the ARRA-principles is directly assigned to the Universities' Vice Rector for Research and Innovation. Furthermore, topics of equality, diversity and inclusion that are central to this endeavor are anchored at our Universities' management level through the Vice Rector for University Culture and its unit Equity, Diversity and Inclusion.

The project of reforming research assessment is embedded in a governance structure that underlines that it is given priority by the university leadership. As such, it will comply with and complement core policies of our University such as the guideline for appointment procedures³, the leadership guidelines⁴, the guidelines for good supervision of doctoral candidates⁵ and adopted policies of good research practice.⁶

This action plan outlines how the University will generate a portfolio of potential measures that may be chosen from in order to apply appropriate and fair practices and mechanisms for the evaluation of researchers and research projects at our institution. As a living document, the Action Plan of the University of Freiburg can be updated any time, if required.

³ <https://uni-freiburg.de/universitaet/verwaltung/service/berufungsleitfaden/>

⁴ <https://uni-freiburg.de/en/university/career-and-human-resources-development/leadership-guidelines/>

⁵ <https://uni-freiburg.de/frs-en/grace/doctoral-studies-ufr/supervision-culture/guidelines-good-supervision/>

⁶ See furthermore the guidelines concerning academic integrity; on handling research data; on open science and on the use of generative AI in research (<https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/good-research-practice/>).

By becoming a member of CoARA, we have committed to the following core principles of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), recognising that a shift towards these principles is perpetual and thus takes time to be put into practice:

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
- Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.

2. Reforming Research Assessment at UFR: From Commitment to Action

In May 2025, the University of Freiburg became a member of CoARA. We have thus committed to critically reviewing and reflecting on existing practices and mechanisms of research evaluation in relation to the commitments outlined above, to which we adhere as an institution. We understand the evaluation of researchers, research outputs and research-conducting entities as a genuine crosscutting topic that affects all of our universities' research community. By focusing on the key stakeholders at our institution, we designed our process of reforming research assessment accordingly.

Steps on our Reform Journey

In order to define the process of reforming research assessment according to the features of our institution and in compliance with the ARRA-principles outlined above, we undertook the following steps aligned with the SCOPE-principle "evaluate with the evaluated".⁷

1. First and foremost, the **University provided human resources** through the position of a consultant responsible for the project of reforming research assessment practices at our institution. The **project is directly assigned to the Vice Rector for**

⁷ The SCOPE Framework (Start Context Options Probe Evaluate) was developed by the REG as a practical way of implementing responsible research evaluation principles to design robust evaluations. It operates under three main principles: 1. Evaluate only where necessary. 2. Evaluate with the evaluated. Any evaluation should be co-designed and co-interpreted by the communities being evaluated. 3. Draw on evaluation expertise (<https://inorms.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/21655-scope-guide-v10.pdf>)

Research and Innovation and thus anchored at the universities' management level. This underlines the scope and the importance of the endeavor for our institution as a whole.

2. We chose a mixture of a top-down and a bottom-up driven process as a **hybrid approach** for reforming Research Assessment at our institution. In order to combine the ground level input of the persons directly involved in research assessment practices, on the one hand, with the universities' overall strategy on the other, we initiated an **internal dialogue**. It is designed to regularly and actively involve relevant stakeholders with different backgrounds in the process of critically reviewing and, where necessary, reforming our practices of research assessment. Hence, we proceeded threefold:
 - In the first place, we exchanged with the Deans resp. the Faculty's executive boards on their **current practices of research assessment**. Their points of view and firsthand accounts as persons who either regularly evaluate and/or are being evaluated themselves, are indispensable to succeed in our Reform Journey. Also, we disseminated information about our Universities membership in CoARA and the project of reforming research assessment at our institution. The **suggestions and expectations expressed by the faculties' representatives** were an essential step in order to proceed on our Reform Journey.
 - In addition, a working group on behalf of the Universities' central administration has been set up. It gathers expertise of research managers and representatives from departments regularly involved in research assessment. The group is chaired by the Vice Rector for Research and Innovation and monitors that the newly developed practices, mechanisms and categories of Research Assessment **align with the broader strategic foci of our institution**. It gathers representatives of the following departments:
 - Department of Equity, Diversity and Academic Personnel Development
 - Office of Committees and Appointments
 - Freiburg Graduate Centre
 - Department of Strategy and University Development

- Deputy Director of the University Library
 - Open Access Commissioner
 - EU Office
 - Controlling and Information Management
 - Head of the Information System on Research Data
- Through bilateral exchanges with the Equal Opportunities Officer of our University, with researchers of different career stages and research managers, we covered specific aspects of research assessment separately, where necessary.
3. As a result of this internal process, we identified **institutional fields of action** to address. On our reform journey, they represent our priorities, as outlined below. Within these fields of action and together with the stakeholders involved in Research Assessment, the University will **elaborate and refine its measures, tools and practices**.
 4. In addition, we **analysed the existing policies, frameworks and guidelines** of our institution with regards to their compliance with the ARRA commitments and vice versa. By identifying overlaps, redundancies or desiderata we narrowed the focus of the core issues to address when evolving the ARRA commitments at our institution.
 5. The **CoARA-Action Plan** of our University has been **adopted by the Rectorate and the Senate in April 2026**. The elected members of these two central governance bodies have thereby approved the content of the Action Plan within our institution. They represent the diversity and wide range of our scientific community: the rector and vice rectors, the head of administration, the legal advisor to the rector, Equal Opportunities Officer, representatives of the staff committee, ECRs of different career stages, students, knowledgeable staff members and the deans of the eleven faculties.

3. A Milestone on our Reform Journey:

An Institutional Guideline for Research Assessment

As an institution, we provide and constantly develop the conditions that enable persons involved in research assessment to deploy with ease the ARRA-principles mentioned above, on an operational level. As an important milestone on our reform journey, we will therefore generate an institutional Guideline of Research Assessment. It addresses members of our institution who evaluate research and research outputs or are evaluated themselves, including all career stages of researchers R1, R2, R3, R4.⁸

The guideline shall be applicable in different contexts and thus has a multi-layered impact within our institution and beyond. On the one hand, it will provide guidance and orientation for those who assess researchers, research outputs and/or research-conducting entities. On the other hand, the guideline will provide reliability and transparency for those who are being assessed, as they can relate to the values and criteria they are evaluated by. As an example for existing categories of Individual Research Assessments at our University, which can be included in our future institutional Guideline, the Annex of this Action Plan displays already established Evaluation Criteria for Tenure-Track-Professorships.

With regards to the ARRA principle of conducting context-sensitive assessments of researchers, research outputs and its entities, the internal guideline will furthermore safeguard the specificities of each discipline. Its purpose is to display options and best practices for research assessment rather than defining processes in detail. It shall serve as a blueprint that can be adapted with regards to the goal (Why do we assess? What or who do we assess?) and with regards to the context it is applied in (Recruitment processes? Peer-Review?).

In order to foster the ongoing development of Research Assessment practices at the University of Freiburg and as a result of systematically monitoring them, the internal guideline will be regularly evaluated and, if necessary, updated.

⁸ The concept of specific career stages was introduced by the framework of the European Commission in terms of functions and experience levels of researchers (<https://www.more-4.eu/indicator-tool/career-stages-r1-to-r4>). R1: First Stage Researcher (up to the point of PhD), R2: Recognised Researcher (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent), R3: Established Researcher (researchers who have developed a level of independence), R4: Leading Researcher (researchers leading their research area or field).

4. Reforming Research Assessment at UFR: Institutional Fields of Action and Measures to be taken

The University of Freiburg decided to pursue a holistic approach of research assessment, acknowledging that excellence manifests differently across research domains and disciplines. This approach includes diverse formats of scientific output and, accordingly, diverse approaches to assess them, including qualitative parameters as well as the responsible use of quantitative metrics. In order to achieve even more comprehensive, context-sensitive and more qualitatively focused evaluations at our institution, we intend to broaden the spectrum of performance dimensions taken into account when conducting assessment on different levels, in particular the assessment of researchers and of research outputs.

Therefore, we refer to our high standards of good research practice applying to all disciplines, as defined in our institutional Guidelines concerning Good Research Practice.¹ Conducting research in line with these quality standards shall not only lead to excellent processes and results of research, but also stand at the core of their evaluation. Thus, our existing Guidelines constitute the conceptual pillars of our reform journey of Research Assessment.²

We identified two *institutional fields of action* of critically reflecting and, where necessary, reforming assessment practices of research. With the aim of implementing our initiative as soon as possible, we will tackle these fields in the following order:

1) Institutional Field of Action: Procedures of Appointment, Recruitment and Promotion (starting in 2026)

- Reviewing Assessment criteria in the context of Appointment procedures
- Reviewing Assessment criteria in the context of Tenure-Track and Juniorprofessor-Evaluations
- Reviewing Assessment criteria and processes of recruiting ECRs and evaluating their academic qualification in the context of (general) Doctoral Degree Regulations and regulations for Habilitation

¹ <https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/good-research-practice/>.

² Our institutional regulation of Academic Integrity is based on the principles adopted by the German Research Foundation (DFG 2019: <https://zenodo.org/records/14281892>). It is designed as an implementation of their general "Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice" and summarizes the core standards of good research practice: <https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/good-research-practice/academic-integrity/>.

2) Institutional Field of Action: Assessment of Researchers and Projects

- Once the *institutional field of action* mentioned above has been successfully reviewed and, where necessary, complemented and/or reformed, we will then address the Performance-oriented Allocation of Funds and Assessment of Researchers and Projects.

Therefore, we will regularly update this Action Plan, showcasing the steps of our Reform Journey and sharing the process of Reforming Research Assessment at our institution with the CoARA community.

In order to concretely tackle both *fields of action* in the future, we will develop an **Institutional Guideline for Research Assessment** as a central portfolio of methods for research assessment and a milestone in our Reform Journey by 2028. As a blueprint, the Guideline will display best practices, options and a toolbox of assessment criteria to apply by researchers who conduct evaluations, including the responsible use of un-biased quantitative parameters. As examples of such potential qualitative and quantitative criteria, see Annex 1) and 2) of this Action Plan.

The table below provides an overview of existing processes and tools of research assessment at our institution as well as planned actions aligning with CoARA's core commitments, where the Guideline will serve as a concrete tool for evolving our processes of research assessment.

With regards to the feasibility of these measures we strive to embed them in our institutional structures and elaborate them with the relevant stakeholders involved (faculties, research administration as outlined above) and in compliance with existing frameworks, policies and guidelines of our institution. These measures are scaled on a five-year period by CoARA, but can be adjusted by our institution any time, if necessary.

Reforming Research Assessment at the University of Freiburg

(Levels of Assessment: Researchers - Research Outputs - Research-conducting Entities)

CoARA Commitments and Guiding Questions	Status quo of Research Assessment in Institutional Guidelines, Frameworks, Policies	Institutional fields of action and Planned Measures
<p>1. CoARA-Commitment: Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research</p> <p>How does your organisation plan to enable greater diversity in career paths and profiles?</p>	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With regards to the Assessment of Researchers, our institutional Guideline for Appointment Procedure is central and as such, regularly updated. It already aligns with a wide range of the CoARA core commitments, in particular regarding measures of equal opportunities. Recently, it was complemented by a mandatory assessment of leadership and supervision skills. • In addition, our institution has signed the voluntary commitment "Towards greater gender equality in appointments" in 2025, initiated by the German Rectors' Conference (https://www.hrk.de/themen/hochschulsystem/gleichstellung/geschlechtergerechtigkeit-bei-berufungen-selbstverpflichtung-der-deutschen-hochschulen/) 	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The University currently reviews and reflects on its evaluation criteria in the context of Procedures of Appointment, Recruitment and Promotion, such as appointments of professors, and the evaluation of junior professorship- and tenure track evaluations. • The same is true for our guidelines that we intend to revise regarding the selection of personnel when recruiting academic (and administrative/non-academic) profiles. • As an institution, we are about to develop an institutional Guideline of Research Assessment, involving all relevant stakeholders by following the principle "evaluate with the evaluated". The guideline shall provide guidance in assessing individuals with focusing more on ideas and less on metrics. In the guideline we will elaborate a set of categories, options and best practices to consider when evaluating individual careers

How does your organisation plan to enable recognition of more diverse contributions to research?

- The University of Freiburg acknowledges leadership and supervision skills as a core qualification in academic job positions. Recently, we adopted our **Central Leadership Guidelines** (<https://uni-freiburg.de/en/university/career-and-human-resources-development/leadership-guidelines/>). We thereby professionalise and provide training in leadership and supervision skills, which are addressed in assessment contexts as such.

Level of Assessment: Research output

- In appointment procedures and Tenure-Track evaluations a **great variety of scientific output** is recognized. In these procedures of assessment, we already take into account innovative formats of research outputs.
- Concerning the publication of research outputs, the University of Freiburg has defined high standards of **Open Science** (<https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/good-research-practice/open-science-policy-of-the-university-of-freiburg/>) and **Research Data Management** ([within a transparent process of assessment.](https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/good-research-practice/policy-on-the-handling-of-research-</div><div data-bbox=)

- The University fosters greater diversity in academic career paths by its new framework **Freiburg Career Paths in Academia**. It introduces three job profiles beyond professorship - lecturer, researcher and academic manager. We thereby acknowledge and valorise a broader spectrum of qualifications and activities that enable excellence in research, teaching and transfer.

Level of Assessment: Research output

- In order to systematically broaden the spectrum of acknowledged formats of scientific outputs, our institution plans to advise the use of the **hybrid CV template of the DFG** to our researchers in our **Guideline for Research Assessment**. The positive effects of this template have been assessed by the DFG (<https://zenodo.org/records/18314376>), as it pays tribute to the diverse formats research outputs are nowadays published in, as well as it pays tribute to early career stages by recognising f.e. pre-print publications as valuable scientific contributions, enabling an adequate and just evaluation of ECRs among others. (In category B of the DFG CV-template “any other form of published results” can be listed, as for example contributions to non-peer-reviewed conferences, articles on preprint servers, data sets, protocols of clinical trials, software packages, patents

	<p>data-at-the-university-of-freiburg/) as a core elements of its own research culture and thus the assessment of any publication format. The <i>University Library</i> and the <i>Central Data Facility</i> already support all researchers of the University of Freiburg with the implementation of these policies.</p>	<p>applied for and granted, blog contributions, infrastructures or transfer. Further forms of academic output can be indicated, such as contributions to the (technical) infrastructure of an academic community, including in an international context, and contributions to science communication:</p> <p>https://www.dfg.de/en/news/news-topics/announcements-proposals/2022/info-wissenschaft-22-61)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The University aims to document its progress in the implementation of the Open Science Transformation and to aggregate its activities. The assessment procedure and data suitable for publication will be made available transparently, in machine-readable form, and under a free license on the website of the University of Freiburg. A condition for documenting open science practices and exploiting their potential is the use of persistent identifiers. All members of the University who conduct research are asked to register for an 'open researcher and contributor identity' (ORCID).• The University Library is about to set up Freiburg University Publishing (FreiUP). The establishment of FreiUP is expected to strengthen the institution's digital sovereignty, to reduce dependency on commercial publishers, to provide a sustainable university-led Diamond Open Access publishing platform, to ensure subject-specific review processes and to promote bibliodiversity by supporting innovative and enhanced publication formats.
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<p>2. CoARA-Commitment: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators</p> <p>How does your organisation plan to accommodate qualitative evaluation mechanisms and base the use of metrics in a way that is aligned with your organisation's value system?</p> <p>How does your organisation plan to</p>	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative peer review already constitutes a central part in the assessment of researchers at our institution, f.e. in the statutes and quality assurance concepts for junior professorships and tenure-track professorships. • With regards to doctoral candidates we provide diversity-sensitive support that adjusts to individual careers and qualifications as defined in our Guidelines for Good Supervision of Doctoral Candidates (https://uni-freiburg.de/frs-en/grace/doctoral-studies-ufr/supervision-culture/guidelines-good-supervision/). • We are about to review mechanisms and processes for assessing researchers at our university. We commit pursuing a responsible use of quantitative metrics in that context by increasing the number of parameters taken into account. In addition, we strive to elaborate methodologies, counting on bias-free performance metrics (f.e. not taking into account the Journal Impact Factor). 	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2028, we plan to adopt an institutional Guideline for Research Assessment, which embraces the CoARAs core commitments as well as our institutional values. It will strongly encourage assessors to take into account a broader variety of practices and contributions to science than on traditional formats of research output as journal articles or papers only. • Our understanding of supporting Early Career Researchers in an adequate way includes to transparently communicate and introduce them to procedures, tools and criteria they are evaluated by at our institution. Thus, we commit to complementing our doctoral degree regulations by the institutional guideline of research assessment mentioned above. The guideline will be designed as a blueprint that can be adjusted with regards to the discipline-specific features within the faculties. In order to implement quality standards for the completion of thesis. • The same is true for Mid-Career Researchers, as we will review the Regulations for Habilitation likewise.
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<p>actively engage in and learn from research on research work?</p>		
<p>3. CoARA-Commitment: Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index</p> <p>How does your organisation plan to mitigate reliance on JIF and h-index?</p>	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligning with this CoARA-Principle, our institutional regulation on safeguarding Academic Integrity already highlights a qualitative approach of research assessment: “In order to evaluate a researcher’s performance, a multidimensional approach is required: In addition to academic performance, other aspects may be taken into account. The evaluation of performance primarily follows qualitative standards, whereby quantitative indicators can only be included in the overall evaluation in a differentiated and reflected manner. As far as freely indicated, individual characteristics in CVs are also included in the assessment.” (see §7 Performance dimensions and evaluation criteria: https://uni-freiburg.de/en/wp-content/uploads/sites/61/Uni-Freiburg-Ordnung-Redlichkeit-in-der-Wissenschaft-en.pdf) 	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In our institutional Guideline of Research Assessment we will recommend best practices of qualitative approaches for purposes of the assessment of research proposals and individual achievements. We will raise awareness for “inappropriate uses” of these parameters as proxies for quality and impact, in particular with regards to persons responsible for bibliometric analysis. Important institutional fields of action where the Guideline is applicable as a tool to adequately and responsibly apply quantitative proxies are Appointment and Recruitment Procedures.

Level of Assessment: Research Outputs

- We aim to retain or regain sovereignty over the evaluation of our researchers and their research outputs by strongly supporting practices of **Open Science**, as outlined in our existing policy. The consideration of data, software, OER, patents, or books in addition to the classic journal article allows a differentiated assessment of scholarly performance beyond performance assessments on the basis of commercially driven quantitative indices as the journal impact factor. This establishes a qualitative view of the performance of researchers and allows disciplinary and cultural as well as personal characteristics to be taken into account when assessing performance (see IX. Evaluation and monitoring: <https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/good-research-practice/open-science-policy-of-the-university-of-freiburg/>). The benefits of diversifying the formats of research outputs that are being assessed as well as the methodologies of assessment have been outlined above, with regards to the DFG-template as well as to the assessment of researchers and projects.

<p>4. CoARA-Commitment: Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment</p> <p>How does your organisation plan to mitigate reliance on organisation rankings?</p>	<p>This Action Plan currently focuses on the assessment of researchers and research outputs rather than on assessing research-conducting entities as departments, institutes or faculties at our University.</p> <p>Rankings in which the University of Freiburg is listed are currently monitored but are not used for research assessment at our University. We are aware of problematic features and effects of global university rankings and thus are taking them into account in a critical and differentiated manner. The University of Freiburg explicitly supports the use of disclosed methodologies and freely accessible data for analysis and results, such as those presented in the Leiden Ranking Open Edition. We equally proceed with regards to bibliometric indices, which we consider as useful as additional information, depending on the discipline, and not as prime factor for scaling the quality of research. Concerning our benchmarking practices, we follow the principle to compare within each faculty or discipline in a context-sensitive way, that is like with like.</p>
<p>5. CoARA-Commitment: Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to</p> <p>Which resources will your institution allocate to the implementation of the</p>	<p>In order to launch the institutional process of reforming research assessment and coordinating our membership within CoARA, the University provided human resources through the position of a consultant responsible. The project is directly assigned to the Vice Rector for Research and Innovation and thus anchored at the universities' management level. Since reforming research assessment within an academic institution is an iterative process per se, we will assess our progress and decide on necessary resources when adopting our institutional guideline of research assessment by 2028.</p>

<p>research assessment reform? (Whether in terms of capacity or budget, to actively engage in the reform Journey)</p>		
<p>6. CoARA-Commitment: Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes</p> <p>Does your organisation plan to pilot or implement alternative/new assessment criteria, tools, and processes (e.g. narrative CV format, competency-based CV format, evidence-based</p>	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> We are currently revising our procedure of Tenure Track evaluations by streamlining them in favor of an even more transparent and a less complex administrative process. The evaluation criteria applied within that process shall base on the planned institutional Guideline of Research Assessment. In order to adequately assess the milestones and efforts of each individual career, we strive to elaborate categories that correspond and are adjustable to the career paths. We intend to streamline the administrative process of evaluation by focusing on the personnel development of each Early and Mid-Career Researcher. Our institution offers a wide range of workshops and trainings to promote a university culture that is free of prejudice and sensitive to discrimination. The offer includes introductory awareness-raising sessions, training in countering bias and prejudice, and 	<p>Level of Assessment: Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resources will be allocated to implement the LA2 software in collaboration with the faculties. Their discipline-specific needs and priorities in appointment procedures will be at the core of costumising and configuring the software. Thus, context-sensitive appointment procedures will be safeguarded. For the responsible, context-sensitive and comparable assessment of researchers, we plan to advise the use of the hybrid CV template of the DFG, that has been adopted in 2022 and “allows applicants to provide both narrative and tabular information, thereby facilitating a holistic view of the applicant’s academic career in the review and evaluation process. (...) As such, the template provides the basis for a qualitatively sound assessment of academic performance that takes greater account of the respective stage of the individual’s life and career. Accordingly, reviewers are now instructed to consider applicants’ academic performance in the context of their individual curriculum vitae and career stage.” <p>(https://www.dfg.de/en/news/news-topics/announcements-</p>

<p>CV format, diversification of research careers and associated career progression)?</p>	<p>courses on protection against discrimination as well as diversity-sensitive personnel selection. These trainings could be customised to brief members of appointment commissions on the consequences of selection criteria and processes in place and the importance to critically reflect them on the long run (https://uni-freiburg.de/gdape-en/workshop-and-training-offers/).</p>	<p>proposals/2022/info-wissenschaft-22-61)</p> <p>In our future Guideline of Research Assessment we are planning to introduce it as a valuable tool for the evaluation of individual career paths.</p>
<p>7. CoARA-Commitment: Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use</p> <p>Does your institution plan to provide training, guidance and support to assessment panels, committees, and juries?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When adopting the institutional Guideline for Research Assessment by 2028, the University will support its implementation in collaboration within the faculties. Newly appointed professors as well as newly hired researchers of all career stages and with different profiles should get acquainted with the institutional Guideline as an integral part of transparent evaluation criteria. • Thus, they will be included in our institutional onboarding-measures and trainings, addressing researchers of all career stages – researchers of career level R1 through our unit The Graduate Centre (GraCe) and researchers of career level R2-R4 through our Centre for Advanced Researcher Development (CARD): https://uni-freiburg.de/en/university/career-and-human-resources-development/startufr/. • We can build upon the following existing formats in order to disseminating knowledge and offer trainings on our institutional standards of research assessment, such as onboarding events for newly appointed deans of faculties. • Our institutional Research Board (https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/research-boards/#Research-Board), responsible for processes of the selection of researchers and processes of peer-review in the context of intramural funding lines and awards (f.e. university scholarships; Innovationsfond Forschung among others) have to be trained in practicing research assessment in line with our institutional Guideline of Research Assessment. • Furthermore, we will systematically include our Guideline in existing frameworks and policies in order to disseminate and safeguard our high standards of research assessment (f.e. in our guideline of appointment procedures, for Good Supervision of Doctoral Candidates, in personnel recruitment and development concepts etc.). 	

<p>8. CoARA-Commitment: Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition</p> <p>How does your organisation plan to exchange practices and foster exchange of good practices in national and international contexts?</p>	<p>Since joining CoARA as a member in 2025, the University of Freiburg participates in exchanges, workshops and discussions hosted by the CoARA-National Chapter Germany. In addition, the University exchanges with CoARA-working groups, where necessary, through its counselor for research assessment.</p> <p>The University of Freiburg is member in broad variety of associations and networks fostering research, teaching, transfer, academic careers and governance. We can benefit from these platforms in order to disseminate information on current developments in reforming systems of research assessment or follow the latest recommendations and expertise. Besides CoARA, our institution is member in:</p> <p>European level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • League of European Research Universities (LERU) • European University Alliance (EPICUR) <p>National level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • German U15 • German Rectors' Conference (HRK) • State Rectors' Conferences (LRK) • The German University Association for the Qualification of Early-Career Researchers in Germany (UniWinD) <p>Regional level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The European Campus (EUCOR) 	
<p>9. CoARA-Commitment: Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Since joining CoARA in May 2025, the University launched an internal dialogue, involving all relevant stakeholders of the faculties and research departments (through Kick-Offs, Meetings and bilateral exchanges). Details of the process are outlined above. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The milestones of the institutional reform journey of research assessment will be published on the Universities websites and in the newsroom. • Changes or adjustments within procedures of appointment or internal evaluations have to be adopted by the academic bodies and will be communicated to all members of the University. • The latest developments concerning Research Assessment at our

<p>How will your organisation ensure the transparent communication of the organisation's research evaluation processes within and outside of the organisation?</p>		<p>University will be included on the landing page on Quality Assurance of Research: https://uni-freiburg.de/en/research/quality-assurance/ as well as outlined in our tailor-made Newsletters for the specific peer-groups (doctoral candidates; postdocs; etc.).</p>
<p>10. CoARA-Commitment: Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research</p> <p>How does your</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through the central governance bodies of our institution, the Rectorate and the Senate, assessment procedures and criteria are regularly being monitored in order to check if they are still up to date. • As soon as our central Guideline of Research Assessment will be adopted by 2028, we will proceed likewise by regularly evaluating the state of affairs regarding our institutional criteria, mechanisms and processes of research assessment in place. • Through the 2030 Female Professors Programme, the University of Freiburg will continue developing its measures for the promotion of gender equality, such as transitional funding for female researchers and gender equality monitoring. Within that framework, the monitoring of data concerning gender equality at our 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our institution launched the implementation of a Central Research Information System (RIS) in respect to the following context: The Commission for Research Information in Germany (KFiD; https://kfid-online.de/) aims to establish the Core Data Set for Research (KDSF Standard - Kerndatensatz Forschung https://www.kerndatensatz-forschung.de/index.php?id=home) as the national standard for the exchange of research information within the academic system, in line with the recommendations of the German Science and Humanities Council. The KDSF provides a standardised framework of defined reporting indicators to harmonize research reporting across academic institutions. Its adoption promotes comparability, transparency, and professional research information. Implementing RIS management will enable structured, KDSF-compliant data collection and management of research information related to

<p>institution plans to monitor and (re)evaluate its assessment criteria, tools, and processes? What will be the frequency? Who will be involved in the evaluation?</p>	<p>institution can indicate where we might have to adjust our measures of institutional research assessment on our way towards a gender-equal university (https://uni-freiburg.de/en/the-2030-female-professors-programme-the-university-of-freiburg-has-received-funding-for-equity-projects/).</p>	<p>Projects, Publications, and Patents, Research infrastructures, Collaborations, Awards, Researchers and organizational units. This will strengthen strategic governance, ensure reliable reporting to external stakeholders and funders, and support transparent presentation of research performance. To support this strategy, the University of Freiburg is implementing a research information system (FIS) that ensures KDSF compliant data collection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the goal of developing a set of responsible parameters of research evaluation, we will further expand and re-evaluate the proven data-aggregation and analysis processes carried out by our Controlling unit. By doing so, we will base our future institutional approaches of research assessment on a solid data foundation.
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Annex 1) to the UFR-CoARA Action Plan

List of Criteria for Evaluating Junior Professorships at the University of Freiburg

A. Research

1. Research foci and projects
 - a. Contribution to research in the relevant field
 - b. Originality of the research approach
 - c. Willingness and ability to conduct interdisciplinary research
 - d. Significance of the research in international comparison
2. Publications: monographs, book chapters, articles in peer-reviewed journals, conference papers (peer-review)
 - a. Plausibility, methodological soundness, and innovative nature of the research project or contribution to the development of the research field
 - b. Citations of the publications and impact factors of the journals
 - c. Reception and evaluation of the research publications
3. Activities as an editor or reviewer for scientific journals and other publications
4. Scientific talks and awards
5. Authorship of expert reports commissioned by science organisations or the like
6. Any appearances on candidate lists for professorships
7. Scientific collaborations with other university and non-university research institutions, international collaborations, joint publications, scientific conferences
8. Third-party funding (amount, institution)
9. Transfer activities (business and industry, public administration, politics) or cooperation with professional practice
10. Support of early career researchers (successful supervision of doctoral candidates and postdoctoral researchers, quality of the graduates' subsequent positions or professional careers)

B. Teaching

1. Subject knowledge (theoretical foundations, subject-specific teaching skills)
2. Range of teaching activities
3. Teaching skills (communication, presentation of knowledge, teaching materials, etc.)
4. Use of multimedia and development of student media competence
5. Evaluation of teaching by students
6. Teaching awards
7. Supervision of degree theses and activity as an examiner
8. Advising skills
9. Internationality

C. Leadership skills

1. Further training and qualification programs completed (at and outside of the university)
2. Documentation of leadership experience (research group leadership, results of any surveys of group members by the Faculty Board)

D. Academic self-government

1. Involvement in departmental and university committee work
2. Activities on behalf of science organisations or professional associations

Annex 2) to the UFR-CoARA Action Plan

Responsible Use of Quantitative Categories at the University of Freiburg

The evaluation of academic performance should not be based on criteria that significantly vary across disciplinary cultures, gender or other diversity parameters. Consequently, publication output is difficult to account for and parameters like the Journal-Impact-Factor or the Hirsch-index have frequently been criticised in that regard. Hence, these parameters are not part of this list.

Assessment of researchers and - to some extent - research projects may draw on achievements in research, teaching, supervision, academic visibility and transfer activities.

Potential categories for performance assessment include:

- The Category *Research* may include third party personnel funding secured per calendar year. To allow for disciplinary differences only personnel is considered and not instrumentation or consumables.
- The Category *Teaching* may include the number of theses (e.g. B.Sc.; M.Sc.; B.A.; M.A.) per professorship or teaching unit in a given time. Theses finished within plus two semesters of standard period of study may be considered in order to comply with teaching requirements.
- The Category *Supervision* may include the number of doctoral dissertations supervised as primary advisor per year. In order to avoid abuse of this parameter, a maximum number of theses per year, e.g. two, should be considered.
- The Category *Academic Visibility* may include parameters such as membership in university bodies (e.g. senate, faculty council, appointments committees) or elevated roles in the academic system (e.g. DFG panels, editor roles, advisory roles for politics). A positive list of parameters has to be agreed upon by the respective discipline.
- The Category *Transfer Activity* may include parameters from the transfer dimensions technology (e.g. patents), knowledge (e.g. significant science communication activities) and education. A positive list of parameters has to be agreed upon by the respective discipline.

All five categories may be evaluated proportionally across the researchers concerned. Each may be weighted equally or special emphasis can be given to certain parameters.